

Open & Transparent Research Practices

Case Study – Literature (Modern Language, Literature and Linguistics)

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Introduction

Openness and transparency constitute a foundational principle for research integrity, as set out in the UK Concordat to Support Research Integrity. Openness can promote rigour, constructive scrutiny, accountability and can enable others to build on research. However, it can also bring challenges. Critically, what openness and transparency can and should mean varies across disciplines and fields of study. This is one of a series of case studies in a wide range of disciplines that illustrate these differences. The series is intended to enable researchers to see similarities and differences between fields, and to inform those supporting open research through, for example, training, policies or incentives. This case study is from the field of Modern Language, Literature, and Linguistics. It is based on a single interview with a researcher, and is therefore illustrative rather than representative.

Background

This case study features Professor Martin Eve, an established scholar in the field at Birkbeck College, University of London. Martin's interests span traditional theoretical work published in articles, book chapters and monographs and translational work on open publishing in the humanities. His research focuses on both contemporary American and British fiction, and on various academic and fiction publishing cultures. The latter explores the sociological reception of contemporary literature and the conditions under which authors write, disseminate and propagate their work. It spans a broad range of topics; from how various market and prize cultures condition the way fiction writers work, through to the publication and funding pressures that shape scientific literature and how academics work and disseminate their findings.

The work itself ranges from simple desk / library based research, where one sits with a laptop, reading everything written on a topic and synthesising this into new forms of argument, through interviews with contemporary authors, to applying computational tools to mine text and study large volumes of writing at scale. Theoretical work tends to be conducted solo or in collaboration with one other person, while translational work, exploring open access in the humanities and business models that could support open publishing, can be grant funded and employ a team of people.

Findings are disseminated via conferences (263 presentations in the past decade), alongside traditional publishing (all open access where possible for both current and historical works), social media and blogging. As much of the core audience of the translational impact work are outside of academia – primarily libraries and publishers – it's essential to target outlets where these stakeholders are most likely to see it.

Relevance of openness & transparency

Currently openness and transparency are not hugely valued in the discipline as a whole with traditional indicators of esteem far outweighing any reward openness is considered to bring. **It is the publication itself and the esteem of the publishing press that is historically rewarded in this field. With the highest prize being** publication in the top tier press, where readership is exclusive and limited to academics.

Martin, however, talks more of the purpose of conducting research being to share ideas with anyone interested to learn more about the field (in his case arts and culture) and the importance of not restricting it to the few who have access. He wonders “What is the point of doing the research if people cannot read it?”

A background as a computer programmer, used to working in open source, gives Martin this fairly unique perspective on gift economies and how sharing can make you feel hugely rewarded by what you are doing. Most of his colleagues have never experienced that. Reward rather comes from being accepted by the most prestigious publishers and having valued experts in the field praise the work. But as Martin points out, these two outcomes do not have to be mutually exclusive. There is no harm in asking the prestigious press who are offering you a book contract what their approach to open access is. In fact, in his role as editor at a Bloomsbury Academic Book series, he is seeing this issue raised more frequently. Although perhaps currently driven more by fear of impending mandates from funders, than an inherent drive to make their scholarship open to all, this people pressure will force the publishers to embrace open access.

Beyond openness of scholarship it is not immediately obvious where transparency of research practice sits in the field. What does reproducibility of research even mean in this discipline, where research typically involves performing and presenting a critical analysis of a particular text? Peer review by well-trained experts in the field already exists precisely to question if the arguments made are plausible, if the evidence from the text supports them and is used judiciously. Pre-registration and the open sharing of code is emerging in the digital humanities – where text based analysis, employing quantitative methods and statistical analysis, is employed - but this aspect of reproducibility otherwise doesn't naturally fit.

Pros and cons of openness & transparency

In this discipline, where openness and transparency of scholarship equates primarily to the open availability of outputs to a general readership the main Pro is that of increased readership. The ease with which materials can be accessed – no need to take a trip to the British Library or wait for an ordered manuscript to be delivered – is something that Martin credits for his above average citation count. Alongside this, at the personal level, sit the career benefits of being an early mover in the jump to open access publishing in the humanities, with this prominent role leading to large grants and an accelerated career path to Professor. From an education perspective ensuring resources are open and freely available solves a problem for overstretched teaching and library budgets, increasingly important in the context of sector wide funding cuts and budget constraints.

Perceived Cons centre primarily around the business model for academic publishing, whereby large manuscript or monograph publishing charges are prohibitive to scholars without access to such funds. Martin argues that this is not a con of open publishing per se, but rather the result of a poor business model that does not work for the good of society. More equitable alternatives are possible that do not make this demand on authors as illustrated by Martin and the Open Library of Humanities.

Cons as espoused by opponents to open publishing also include historical worries that open licensing allows individuals to take the work and pervert its meaning to promote dubious political causes – something that one might doubt copyright laws could prevent regardless. Or that untrained people will simply not understand the work. For some, this exclusivity of

readership perhaps adds to the apparent professionalism of the field and serves to make the topic appear serious and hard to the outsider.

While some may raise concerns about a personal financial hit from open access, in reality the royalties for most academic texts are small (outside perhaps of popular science best sellers or undergraduate text books) and there is no evidence that open access degrades print sales. Open access books are still purchased and do still produce royalties, although eminently practical, e-reading formats are no match to a printed copy and individuals keen to read thousands of words on a topic will likely buy a printed copy if they can.

Wider context & trends

Within the humanities literary studies sits somewhere in the middle with regards to openness and transparency. It is more transparent than some disciplines, less than others. Philosophy has a long culture of sharing working papers, an open access preprint you could say. Here a scholar presents their work broadly, seeking comments and feedback, for some time before a final draft is completed and its sent for publication. You could argue that in this regard they have a long tradition of open, early publication. Medievalists also have a long history of open access publishing. Pre-print servers, while mooted, have thus far enjoyed limited traction in the humanities where the debate around their value continues. Not only would publishers be unlikely to accept work that is already published elsewhere, there is a question of whether a smaller volume of peer reviewed open articles is more valuable to scientific discourse than a larger volume of unchecked materials.

Looking to the future, when change comes, it seems likely it will largely be driven by the funders. Martin would like to see a mandate for open access publishing from the REF consultation, with appropriate funding to make it practically possible. The UKRI open access mandate for books has invested 3.6million into the process but more is needed. Importantly, the previous REF green open access mandate for journal articles has driven huge culture change and a similar move would be very welcome for monographs. Such a move would reap huge benefits both in the volume of materials widely available to society and in making researchers experience for themselves the positive effects of open publishing. Opening their eyes to the benefits for themselves, their scholarship and society should prove to be an important turning point in forging a key place for open access publishing in the future of academic work in the humanities.

Martin also notes that almost every monograph is available digitally and openly, albeit illegally and the system has not crashed as a result. Economic arguments about open access publishing of monographs fall apart when one considers that although the humanities are in formal terms not very open at all, they are in fact very open indeed.

Open Library of the Humanities

The Open Library of the Humanities (OLH) came about as the result of the frustration Martin felt with the economic model proposed for open access in his disciplines and the challenges that this creates. In 2012, when asked what level of author processing charge could work, the answer was a resounding zero! In response, Martin and colleagues built a model where academic libraries pay an annual subscription to them so they can exist as a fully open access humanities publisher. With this funding, they never have to request an Author Processing Charge to authors. Everything is published open access and available to all. When asked what is in it for the libraries, Martin is keen to explain that the libraries get access to everything regardless of their subscriber status, but libraries are such strong advocates of open access that they keen to support it. They see very low rates of cancellation, and gain many more subscribers every year than they lose. As Martin concludes, we are more likely to win the battle of hearts and minds for open access by thinking collectively and working together as a

community to overcome prohibitive costs at the individual level, and ensure humanities scholarship is available to all.

More detail on the OLH can be found here: <https://www.openlibhums.org/>

“The Open Library of Humanities (OLH) is a charitable organisation dedicated to publishing open access scholarship with no author-facing article processing charges (APCs). We are funded by an [international consortium of libraries](#) who have joined us in our mission to make scholarly publishing fairer, more accessible, and rigorously preserved for the digital future. Our mission is to support and extend open access to scholarship in the humanities – for free, for everyone, for ever.”

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